

The Art Historian's Bicycle Becomes an E-Bike

VISART VI - Oct 2022 - Tel Aviv

Workshop at the European Conference of Computer Vision (ECCV)

Etienne Posthumus, Hans Brandhorst, Harald Sack

etienne.posthumus@partners.fiz-karlsruhe.de

FIZ Karlsruhe

Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur

“Computers are bicycles for the mind”

Steve Jobs

A brief intro to Iconclass

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Androcleus section XXV: When he hears his Christian name 'Andreas', Androclus panicks and flees from the lady's bedroom

Telephone numbers for topics

41A23 bedroom

41A76121 two poster bed

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33B9 flight, running away; pursuing

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(+ reaching for somebody or something, seizing something, touching)

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4 · Society, Civilization, Culture

41 · material aspects of daily life

41A · housing

41A7 · furniture and household effects

41A76 · furniture to lie on or in

41A761 · bed

41A7612 · bed with tester

41A76121 two poster bed

Androclus section XXV: When he hears his Christian name 'Andreas', Androclus panicks and flees from the lady's bedroom

Collect it all together....

A collection of circa 750K objects described using ICONCLASS

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This is mostly manual labour, by
specialists. Hence costly.

Can we help?

Browse

Search

sleeping lion

Advanced Search

Exclude keys (+)

Sort by notation

Found 27 results, searching for *sleeping lion*

All

2

3

7

- 34E11(+946) lion's den (+ sleeping animal(s))
- 34E11(+9461) lion's den (+ hibernation of animal(s))
- 34F111(+946) man struggling with animals as ornamental variant with antithetically placed animals (mostly lions) (+ sleeping animal(s))
- 34F111(+9461) man struggling with animals as ornamental variant with antithetically placed animals (mostly lions) (+ hibernation of animal(s))

3 · Human Being, Man in General

34 · man and animal

34E · restraint of animals

34E1 · dangerous wild animals ~ restraint of animals

34E11 · lion's den

34E11(+9) · lion's den (+ zoological aspects of animals ~ man and animal)

34E11(+94) · lion's den (+ animal behaviour)

34E11(+946) **lion's den (+ sleeping animal(s))**

Search with these related keywords:

Verhalten, animal, behaviour, comportamento, comportement, dormir, dormire, human being, lion's den, occupations, pit, restraint, schlafen, sleeping, throwing (being thrown), wild animal

Also see:

31E2365 · violent death by throwing to the wild animals

Add more detail:

34E11(+9461) · lion's den (+ hibernation of animal(s))

Can we help?

Browse

Search

Type some word(s) in English to search for and press 'Enter'...

Advanced Search

Exclude keys (+)

Sort by notation

Found 17 results, searching for *this uploaded image*

- 31A2211 face
- 25F23(LION) beasts of prey, predatory animals: lion
- 25F animals
- 25F23(TIGER) beasts of prey, predatory animals: tiger
- 31B19 resting
- 25F23(LION)(+46) beasts of prey, predatory animals: lion (+ sleeping animal(s))
- 25F23(LION)(+33) beasts of prey, predatory animals: lion (+ head of an animal)
- 25I city-view, and landscape with man-made constructions
- 25F24(DROMEDARY) hoofed animals: dromedary
- 47I2141(+922) he-goat, billy-goat (+ male animal)
- 34B11 dog
- 43B7 zoo (as place of recreation)
- 34E22 zoological garden, zoo, seen as place where non-domestic animals are kept
- 31A24(+1) postures of the head (+ front view)
- 61B(+55) historical persons (portraits and scenes from the life) (+ full length portrait)

Implementation details

Standing on the shoulders of
giants

A giant is carrying the world on his shoulder, and pulling the tables of the Law behind him, tied to his foot with a rope

https://www.arkyves.org/view/folger_ill_063084

Implementation details

OpenAI CLIP - <https://openai.com/blog/clip/>

FAISS - <https://faiss.ai/>

Especially useful is AutoFaiss - <https://github.com/criteo/autofaiss>

Mechanism

- Use Visual Similarity to find matching images
- Extract all ICONCLASS notations
- Sort by Frequency of Usage
- Display top n hits

...iterate.

Browse

Search

Type some word(s) in English to search for and press 'Enter'...

Advanced Search

Exclude keys (+)

Sort by notation

Found 17 results, searching for *this uploaded image*

- 73C1338(+0) the head of John the Baptist on a platter (+ variant)
- 92N1 (story of) Pluto (Hades), Dis Pater, Orcus
- 92B17 specific aspects, allegorical aspects of Jupiter; Jupiter as patron
- 61B(+52) historical persons (portraits and scenes from the life) (+ (full) bust portrait)
- 45C13(SWORD) hacking and thrusting weapons: sword
- 31A2422 head turned to the right
- 12B13 representations ~ gods, demi-gods, heroes, etc. (non-Christian religions)
- 49G3211 dressing, bandage
- 49G3 medical examination, medical treatment
- 73D642 crucified Christ with Mary Magdalene, who usually weeps and embraces the cross
- 42E131 mourning the dead
- 11Q651 crucifix ~ personal devotion

9 - Classical Mythology and Ancient History

92 - gods ~ classical mythology

92B - the great gods of Heaven, and their train

92B1 - (story of) Jupiter (Zeus)

92B17 specific aspects, allegorical aspects of Jupiter; Jupiter as patron

Search with these related keywords:

Jupiter, allegory, ancient history, classical antiquity, gods, heaven, history, mythology, patron

Add more detail:

92B171 - Jupiter as king of Heaven

92B178 - triumph of Jupiter; 'Carro di Giove' (Ripa)

92B179 - veneration of Jupiter

92B17(+0) - specific aspects, allegorical aspects of Jupiter; Jupiter as patron (+ variant)

15 sample images

reserved for caption

reserved for caption

reserved for caption

METALS, Part 5. Chap. 1. fol. 113. Represented by the 7. Deities, who according ...

Balance van den Fransen Oorlog (titel op object)

Zittende Jupiter op een leeuw, op wolken

Future work

Improving the user interface

More bulk data

Allowing Users to interactively annotate datasets and contribute new content